

Managing risks to big stuff: Risk assessment and reduction at the Canada Science and Technology Museum

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A risk management perspective keeps the focus on the goal of preventive conservation, which is to “[convey] a collection, with as much and as many possible values intact, from one point in time to a point in time in the future” (Waller and Michalski 2005, p. 735). To do this, we use an approach that provides:

- a common scale for magnitude of all risks...
- a prediction of the magnitude of each risk if nothing is changed; and,
- a prediction of how these magnitudes will change if certain improvements are made.

(Waller and Michalski 2004, p. 3)

This approach allows those responsible for collections to compare all risks and identify those that could cause the greatest loss in collection value over a certain period. An institution can then devote its limited resources to projects that reduce those risks, projects that will, therefore, have the greatest impact on collections preservation.

In 2009, CCI began a series of pilot risk assessment projects in order to explore the feasibility of this approach to preventive conservation advisory services for Canadian museums and archives. The method used is based on that developed by Stefan Michalski of CCI in collaboration with ICCROM (International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property), the Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed (RCE, the Dutch equivalent of CCI), and Rob Waller, formerly of the Canadian Museum of Nature, for an advanced professional development course to teach conservators and heritage professionals the risk management approach. To date, CCI has completed four collections risk assessments for two historic house museums, an art gallery, and a provincial archives. In addition, CCI has undertaken a risk analysis project for the *Hamilton & Scourge* National Historic Site in which risks are analysed using the expertise of a panel of site management staff and expert partners.

For its fifth comprehensive risk management project, CCI is partnering with the Canada Science and Technology Museums Corporation (CSTMC) to assess the risks to collections for three museums: Canada Science and Technology Museum, Canada Aviation and Space Museum and Canada Agriculture and Food Museum. This project focuses on the risks affecting collection objects on display and in storage in six facilities. The goal of the assessment is to prioritize the risks facing the CSTMC’s collection from all internal and external hazards in order to develop a 5-year plan for collections preservation. The key steps in the project are summarized below.

Establish the Context

Risk assessment always takes place in the context of a specific institution with its particular mission, collections, building, and site. Staff are consulted and institutional documents are reviewed to ensure that the project scope and planning period or “time horizon.” are appropriate. Usually a time horizon of 30 years is used.

Although collecting institutions aim to treat all objects with equal care, most include certain objects or sub-collections that are more important in terms of the mission of the institution and are therefore of greater value to the institution. Damage to such objects or collections will have a great impact on the ability of the institution to fulfil its mission. The Collection Value Pie, a visual representation of the

relative value of different parts of the collection, captures this variation in value between parts of the collection in order that the risk assessment can better express the difference in risk magnitude should more valuable artifacts, records or specimens be affected.

The relative value of parts of CSTMC collection was modelled in collaboration with museum staff. The collection was first divided between three-dimensional objects and two-dimensional objects, then, further into different value groups (high value, “named” collections, average value). Graphs generated by the CCI Database allow museum staff to compare the ranking of risks which accounts for relative object value with one where all objects are considered equal.

Identify Risks

Risk identification and analysis is being completed by conservators and scientists of CCI in collaboration with conservators at CSTMC. Risks include all those that are expected to cause a significant loss of collection value. The risks identified are only those that affect the preservation of the collections. Risks associated with employee health and safety or business continuity are not included. Each risk is described using a specific risk summary sentence that states what the hazard is, what adverse effect it causes, the path the hazard takes to create the adverse effect, and the fraction of the collection that it affects. For example, storage in warehouses at room temperature with poorly controlled relative humidity, pollutant filtration and UV results in the accelerated deterioration of objects or components made of some plastics and rubber.

Analyse Risks

Risks are analysed using the CCI-ICCROM-RCE method and the CCI Collections Risk Management Database. CCI is training CSTMC conservators in this method as part of the project. Analysis consists of answering three questions for each risk:

- How often will the event occur or how soon will the process cause loss?
- How much value will be lost in each object that is affected?
- How much of the collection value is affected?

A numerical score is generated in answering each question. Data required to produce these scores is gathered in conjunction with CSTMC staff using institutional knowledge, collection database information and site visits along with regional statistics on hazards like fire and earthquakes, and published conservation research. Once analysed in this way, the three parameters are scored on a scale up to 5 where 5 represents the highest risk. Uncertainty is also captured through high and low estimates.

The sum of these three scores gives the magnitude of risk score for that specific risk. The risk scale used in the CCI method is an “order of magnitude” scale, like the Richter scale for earthquakes, or the decibel scale for noise. The scale has been set with a maximum of 15, which represents the risk that the whole archival collection (5 points for all the collection) will be totally lost (5 points for total loss of each object) within one year (5 points for the rapidity). Each step lower on the scale (e.g. 15 to 14, 14 to 13, etc.) indicates a risk that is 10 times lower in magnitude. Thus a decrease of 2 steps means a drop by a factor of 100, a decrease of 3 means a factor of 1,000, and so on. An order of magnitude scale is adopted for measuring risk so that a huge range in the size of risks can be discussed side-by-side, without having to use six or seven decimal places.

Evaluate Risks

When analysis is complete, the risks are ranked by magnitude of risk score to establish priorities. CCI classifies the level of specific risks on a scale from low to extreme based on the magnitude of risk score. Risks scoring 10 and higher—high to extreme risks—are priority risks for reduction.

Reduce Risks

For each identified risk, risk reduction options are generated and evaluated. Many options are proposed and those considered most feasible and beneficial are analysed using the CCI Collection Risk Assessment Database in the same manner as for the original risk. The cost of implementing the option is also estimated roughly based on present day costs and the current size of the collection. The cost-effectiveness of each strategy is determined by dividing the reduction in risk magnitude with the cost over the 30-year time horizon. Risk reduction and cost-effectiveness are then used to evaluate the possible options in order to develop strategies that maximize both.

Options that best addressed the priority risks (high and very high risks) are recommended. Responsible institutions will implement plans to reduce such risks so that their magnitude falls closer to or below 10. Reduction of the magnitude of risk score to below 10 for some risks may be difficult in some circumstances. These risks require ongoing vigilance in terms of preventive conservation practice. Medium risks score between 7.5 and 10. In general, these risks should not be considered priorities until the higher risks have been reduced. Staff may nevertheless wish to review all medium risks to identify those that could be easily or cheaply reduced further. Risks scoring below 7.5 are generally adequately managed by the institution. Improvements may still be possible, but these are rarely cost-effective and are generally not recommended for implementation.

Once complete, the risk analyses and evaluation as well as the recommendations for risk reduction will be captured in a report. Because institutional conservators are learning the method as part of the project, CSTMC should have the capacity to monitor and review risks to its collections as they grow and as changes to facilities and collections care practices are implemented.

References

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